

Soil Bacteria Load and the Effect on the Survival of *Archachatina Marginata*

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ABSTRACT

The experiment was carried out for sixty days with soil samples collected from three different locations in Fenders Snail Farm and labelled as L1(undisturbed land), L2(Undisturbed with vegetation) and location L3 (Sandfilled damp land). The study was undertaken to determine the effect of soil bacteria load in three different categories of a snail farm land on the survival of *Archachatina marginata*. The total bacteria count of the soil samples were estimated using the Standard Spread Plate Technique. A pH meter was used to monitor the soil pH. Bacterial isolates were identified based on their cultural, morphological and behavioural characteristics using established characters. Snail species reared on the farm were *Archachatina marginata*. A total of 12 species of bacteria were recorded at the three locations within the farm. The bacteria species were widely distributed except *Alcaligenes Vibrio*, *Klebsiel* and *Proteus* species. The highest number of bacteria was recorded in location L1. *Bacillus* spp was the most dominant bacteria species with the highest Relative Abundance recorded during the study while *Aspergillus* spp was the most dominant fungi species. Bacteria and fungi were typical of an environment with specie richness. The microorganisms isolated are capable of causing diseases in snails especially *Pseudomonas*. There is a need to safeguard snail farms from the outbreak of such mortality-causing diseases.

Keywords: Bacteria, Fungi, Soil, Microorganism, Load, Survival.

INTRODUCTION

Soil is a component of the ecosystem that provide a medium for plant, animal and microbial existence. Soil microbes play crucial roles in enriching the soil and maintaining its structure and fertility. (O'Donnell *et al*, 2001). Bacteria make up the most abundant organism in the soil. Snails are mostly raised on soil thereby altering the physical appearance, chemical and microbial state of the soil. (Nyoagbe *et al*, 2016). This is primarily because snails discharge their waste on the soil. (Ibom *et al*, 2012). This has the possibility of increasing the habitats bacteria load. Bacteria contamination by animal excreta is very common in animal farms. High concentration of bacteria can occur from animal husbandry operations and this can result in health hazards due to the presence of pathogens (Obasohan *et al*, 2010)

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Snail soil tolerance differs. Most land snails including the Giant African land snails prefer soils that are slightly alkaline. Loamy soil (Garden soil) is reported to be the best for snail husbandry. Snail depends very much on soil for food and reproduction. They require moist, aerated, easily drained, non-waterlogged and non-acidic soil rich in mineral content and organic matter. Some reproductive activities of the snail like egg laying are carried out predominantly in the soil. Also, snails require the soil for some nutrients. They get Calcium and some other minerals from the soil. (Ebenso, 2006).

Climate and its effect on soil have an associated effect on snail farming. The effect of heat resulting in high soil temperature could lead to reduced feed intake, reduced body weight, poor hatchability and fertility (Afolabi, 2013). A lot of work has been done on the effect of organic waste on soil but records show that the effect on snail farms are very scanty. (Ekundayo, 2005). The primary aims of the research are to determine the physical parameters of the snail farm soils, study the bacteria dynamics of the soil and how they relate to the survival of *Archachatina marginata*. To achieve this, the research specific objectives are to

- 1, Investigate the bacteria dynamics of the undisturbed and sand filled portions of the farm.
- 2, Determine the cause of the heavy snail mortality the farm has been experiencing in location L3,
- 3, Determine the physical parameters of the three locations and how they affect snail survival.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Experimental Site

The study area is situated at The Federal University of Technology, Akure, south gate located in Ondo State, South West region of Nigeria. Ondo state lies on latitude $05^{\circ} 41' N$ and longitude $06^{\circ} 32' E$. The area lies within the tropical rainforest belt with an annual rainfall of about 1,613 mm and an annual mean temperature of about $27^{\circ}C$. The dry season usually starts in October and ends in March while the rainy season starts in April and ends in October.

Experimental Snails

One hundred and thirtyfive juvenile *Archachatina marginata* (Giant African Land Snail) that is in the family Achatinidae obtained from the NEPA market in Akure (Nigeria) were used in carrying out the experiment. The duration of the experiments was 60 days.

Experimental Material

This experiment involved raising of the snails in three different locations in the farm designated as L1 (undisturbed land), L2 (undisturbed vegetative land) and L3(sand filled damp land) representing the different farm locations and replicated three times. One hundred and thirty-five snails were used for this experiment with 15 snails introduced per replicate. The snails were randomly selected and introduced into the locations and were weighed using the electronic scale to get their initial body weight.

Feeding and Watering

The snails were fed the same diet throughout the experimental period of 60 days. Food and water were given to the snails *ad libitum*. The weight of the snails were taken at the beginning of the

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experiment and subsequently once in 2 weeks to know their response to the different farm soil bacteria conditions. The snails were also being weighed at the end of 60 days. Mortality and survival rates were recorded.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

All snails were kept under the same environmental condition and managed similarly for 60 days. Samples of top-soil that were used for the experiment were collected from three locations and their replicates in the farm. The samples were labelled according to the site of the collection as E1, E2, E3 for location L1 and replicates (undisturbed portion). F1, F2, F3 for location L2 (undisturbed vegetative portion) and replicates and G1, G2, G3 for location L3 and replicates (Sand filled damp portion). The samples collected were top soils (8.5 cm dept) using an 8.5 cm diameter auger. The soil samples were introduced into plastic containers for laboratory analysis.

Sampling

Soil parameters determined were soil pH, soil temperature and soil bacterial load.

The soil samples from the 3 locations were analyzed for bacteria population using the standard spread-plate dilution method by Seely and Vandemark (1981). For bacteria isolation, incubation was done for five days, a nutrient agar (Oxoid) containing 0.015% (w/v) nystatin (to inhibit fungi growth) was used. Incubation was at 35° C for five days.

Sterilization techniques

The polyethylene bags were cold-sterilized in uv-radiation box for at least 12 h (usually overnight), while glassware was treated in the hot-air oven at 160⁰ C for 2 h. Growth media and diluents (distilled water) were autoclaved at 121⁰ C for 15 min.

SNAIL PARAMETERS MEASURED

The parameters measured at the end of the experiment were weight gain using an electronic weighing balance, survival rate and shell length was determined using veneer calliper. The same method was used for shell breadth.

Identification of Isolates

Identification of isolates for the experiment was based on cultural, microscopic and biochemical characteristics with reference to Bergey's manual on determinative bacteriology (1989) for bacteria isolates identification.

Soil PH

Soil pH was determined using the pH meter and according to the procedure described by Ujowundu, *et al* (2011)

Mortality

The snails were monitored on a daily basis to remove the dead ones. Deaths were recorded. Survival percentages were calculated and recorded. The record was used to determine the survival rate. The mortality percentage was also calculated.

Carcass evaluation

At the end of the experiment, three snails per treatment (one per replicate) were randomly selected and weighed for carcass. The snails were starved overnight and slaughtered with the shell removed. The snails were eviscerated and weighed to obtain their dressed carcass weights. The dressed carcass weights were expressed as percentages of the live weights.

Statistical Analysis

All data collected were subjected to one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) using SPSS 15.0. The significance difference among mean was determined by the use of Duncan's Multiple Range Test (Duncan, 1955)

Results And Discussions

Results

Total bacterial counts

The average total bacterial counts (TBC) of each soil sample ranged from 41.00×10^3 colony forming units (cfu) per gram of soil, 35.00×10^3 cfu/g of soil, 25.00×10^3 cfu/g of soil of location L1, L2 and L3 respectively as shown in Table 1. The highest counts were observed in location L1 (38.76) and L2 (35.48%), and the lowest count was observed in L3 (25.80%).

In table 1, twelve species of bacteria were recorded from the three locations of the farm. Twelve species of bacteria were recorded in location L1, eleven species in location L2 and Eight species in location L3. The bacteria species were widely distributed except *Alcaligenes* sp. *Klebsiela*, *proteus* and *Vibrio* sp. which did not show any wide distribution in the three locations.

Table1: Occurrence and abundance of some genera of aerobic heterotrophic bacteria of sampling location.n x 10³ (cfu/g)

Bacteria	L1	L2	L3
<i>Pseudomonas sp.</i>	+	+	+
<i>Xantomonas sp.</i>	+	+	+
<i>Bacillus sp.</i>	+	+	+
<i>Proteus sp.</i>	+	+	-
<i>Chromobacterium sp.</i>	+	+	+
<i>Staphylococcus sp.</i>	+	+	+
<i>Vibrio sp.</i>	+	+	-
<i>Clostridium sp.</i>	+	+	+
<i>Erwinia sp.</i>	+	+	+
<i>Klebsiela sp.</i>	+	+	-
<i>Alcaligenes sp.</i>	+	-	-
<i>Clavibacter sp.</i>	+	+	+
Total	12(38.71%)	11(35.48%)	8(25.80)

+ = Presence; - = absence.

In Table 2, the highest number of bacteria was recorded in location L1 (41). Sizeable number of bacteria species were recorded in the three locations with the location L3(sand filled soil) having the lowest number. *Bacillus sp* was the most abundant species and the least abundant specie was *Alcaligenes sp*.

Table 2: Bacteria abundance recorded in the three locations n x 10³ (CFU/g)

BACTERIA	L1	L2	L3	TOTAL
<i>Pseudomonas sp.</i>	5	3	17	25
<i>Xantomonas sp.</i>	2	2	2	6
<i>Bacillus sp.</i>	9	9	4	28
<i>Proteus sp.</i>	4	3	-	7
<i>Chromobacterium sp.</i>	4	2	1	7
<i>Staphylococcus sp.</i>	5	2	4	11
<i>Vibrio sp.</i>	1	2	-	3
<i>Clostridium sp.</i>	2	2	2	6
<i>Erwinia sp.</i>	1	2	1	4
<i>Klebsiela sp.</i>	2	3	-	5
<i>Alcaligenes sp.</i>	2	-	-	2
<i>Clavibacter sp.</i>	1	2	2	5
Total	38	35	33	106
Number of species	12	11	8	12

Table 3 show *Pseudomonas* spp as the specie with the highest relative abundance during the study. *Bacillus* spp are the second most abundant species recorded. *Alcaligenes* spp have the lowest relative abundance.

Table 3: Relative abundance of some bacteria species found in the snail farm

BACTERIA	L1	L2	L3	MEAN
<i>Pseudomonas sp.</i>	12.19	8.57	51.51	24.09
<i>Xantomonas sp.</i>	4.87	5.71	6.06	5.55
<i>Bacillus sp.</i>	21.95	25.71	12.12	19.93
<i>Proteus sp.</i>	9.75	8.57	-	6.10
<i>Chromobacterium sp.</i>	9.75	5.71	3.03	6.16
<i>Staphylococcus sp.</i>	12.19	5.71	12.12	10.00
<i>Vibrio sp.</i>	2.43	5.71	-	2.71
<i>Clostridium sp.</i>	4.87	5.71	6.06	5.55
<i>Erwinia sp.</i>	2.43	5.71	3.03	3.72
<i>Klebsiela sp.</i>	4.87	8.57	-	4.48
<i>Alcaligenes sp.</i>	4.87	-	-	1.62
<i>Clavibacter sp.</i>	2.43	5.71	6.06	4.73

Table 4 shows Shannon-Wiener and Margalef indices. The indices measure specie richness of a community independent of sample size. Bacteria species richness was most significant at location L1 and less significant at location L3. Location L1 has the highest number of bacteria species indicating highest species diversity. This means that location L1 has greater biological stability while location L3 has less biological stability.

Table 4: Species Diversity value of the bacteria species found in the snail farm

Diversity Indices	L1	L2	L3
Taxas	12	11	8
Individuals	41	32	33
Dominance-D	0.9002	0.8983	0.7224
Shannon- H	2.26	2.24	1.57
Simpson 1-D	0.0998	0.1017	0.2776
Evenness e.H/S	0.9078	0.9323	0.7574
Margalef	3.024	2.8854	2.002

Table 5: Shows the result of the physiochemical parameter measured during the experimental period. Atmospheric temperature range between 28.0oC and 29oC while soil temperature in the location range between 25.4o and 26.8oC. The Soil pH in the location L2 was higher than location L1 and L3. However, difference in the Soil pH values of the different sampling locations were not observed to be statistically significant (P<0.05).

Table 5: Mean value of physicochemical parameter of the farm location for snail survival

Parameters	L1	L2	L3
Atmospheric temp(°C)	28	29	28
Soil temperature(°C)	26.3	26.8	25.4
Soil PH	7.10	7.15	7.09

The pH values ranged from 7.09 – 7.15. The soil pH in location L2 (7.15) was higher than location L1 (7.10) and location L3 (7.09) as shown in Table 5. However, differences in the soil pH values of the different sampling locations were not observed to be statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

Table 6: Growth response and survival rate of *Archachatina marginata* on different soil bacteria conditions

Growth parameters	L1	L2	L3	SEM
Initial body weight(g)	157.51 ^a	158.63 ^a	158.33 ^a	6.62
Final body weight(g)	168.08 ^{ab}	160.93 ^{ab}	181.01 ^b	1.06
Weight gain(g)	10.57 ^a	2.3 ^b	22.62 ^c	1.71
Ave. daily weight gain(g/day)	0.17 ^a	0.04 ^{ab}	0.37 ^{ab}	0.53 ^b
Mortality rate (%)	33 ^b	29 ^b	69 ^a	-
Survival rate (%)	67 ^b	71 ^b	31 ^a	-

+ = Presence; - = absence.

DISCUSSION

A total of 12 species of bacteria were recorded at the three locations within the farm. The bacteria species identified in this study are similar to those mentioned in other reports (Akaninwor *et al*, 2007, Aluyi *et al*, 2006 Agbabiaka and Oyeyiola 2012, Uzoigwe and Agwa, 2012). This research has been able to show that diverse types of bacteria were isolated from a farm location in Akure. Similar results have been reported by Pritchard *et al* (2007) in studies carried out in some communities in South Africa. The sand filled damp portion of the farm (L3) has been witnessing heavy mortality which could be attributed to several factors especially the presence of *pseudomonas* spp of bacteria.

The isolation of bacterial species from the soil showed that more bacteria were observed in the undisturbed snail farm soil L1 and undisturbed vegetative soil L2 than the sand filled damp soil, L3. Of the 12 bacterial species observed in this study, four species were absent in the L3 soil samples unlike the L1 and L2 soil samples which have more species. (Table 1.). The observation agrees with findings by Parham *et al* (2003) and Reverodo and Melo (2007) that increased microbial prevalence in snail farm soil indicate an increase in bacteria nutrient and other conditions for microbial growth. *Pseudomonas*, *Xantomonas*, *Bacillus*, *Chromobacterium*, *Staphilococcus*, *Clavibacter* and *Clostridium* species were all distributed in the three locations as shown in Table 1. This might be due to the presence of suitable habitat and breeding sites. *Alcaligenes* spp was

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found only in location L1. Also, *Vibrio* spp was restricted to location L1 and L2 as shown in Table 1.

The highest number of bacteria was recorded in location L1 (12). This was followed by location L2 (11). The increased bacteria prevalence in the L1 soil samples indicates the increased bacteria nutrient and conditions of bacterial growth. The high prevalence of micro-organism observed in location L1 and L2 agrees with Olaniya (2004). The snail waste could serve as increased additional source of bacteria in the soil. It could also be due to the heavy presence of leaf litters and less volumes of water in the location. This is also the location that recorded the lowest mortality.

Bacillus spp was the most abundant species with the highest abundance recorded (28) during the study as shown in Table 2. *Pseudomonas* spp are the second most abundant species recorded. The highest numbers were recorded at location L3 as shown in Table 2.

Table 3 showed *Baccillus* spp as the specie with the highest relative abundance during the study. *Staphylococcus* spp are the second most abundant species recorded. *Alcaligens* spp have the lowest relative abundance.

Statistical analysis indicates that relative abundance between the locations were not significantly ($P>0.05$) different. Statistically there is no significant ($P>0.05$) difference between the species richness and diversity of the three locations. This may be attributed to the similar vegetation composition, climatic condition and soil condition of the sites. It may also be attributed to the sampling method used.

Shannon-Wiener and Margalef indices measures species richness of a community independent of sample size. Bacteria species richness was most significant at location L1 and less significant at location L3. Location L1 has the highest number of bacteria species indicating higher species diversity. (Table 4) This means that location L1 has greater biological stability while location L3 has less biological stability.

Sorenson quantitative index that was calculated showed that greater number of similar species are recorded at the location. This may be attributed to similarity in soil conditions like depth, size and vegetation cover.

Table 5 shows the physicochemical parameter measured during the experimental period. Atmospheric temperature ranges between 28.00C and 29oC while soil temperature in the location range between 25.40C to 26.80C. The temperature ranges agree with the reports of Ojokoh and Adetunji (2002) as well as Agbabiaka and Oyeyiola (2012), who reported a temperature range of 29 – 30⁰C and 22 – 31⁰C respectively. The result showed increase in L1 and L2 soils more than the L3. The pH range of 7.09 to 7.15 reported in this study was near neutrality. The range was similar to that reported by Uzoigwe and Agwa (2012) on microbial quality of water (6.89) collected near a dump site. Increased pH was observed in L2 soil than the L3 and L1. A similar observation had been reported by Adesemeye *et al* (2006), and Ezeronnye and Ubawa (2005).

Table 6 shows the growth response and survival rate of *Archachatina marginata* on different soil bacteria conditions. The highest body weight was recorded among snails at location L3. This may be attributed to the fact that only few snails competed for the food because of the high mortality recorded at the location. The location witnessed a high mortality rate (69%) and a low survival rate. The location recorded the highest prevalence of *Pseudomonas* which in high dominance is responsible for high mortality in snails. This agrees with findings by Ekwu (2016) who reported that *Pseudomonas* causes intestinal infection that can spread rapidly among snail population leading to high mortality. In Figure 1, no significant difference existed in the survival rate between location L1 and L2 ($P > 0.05$) but they were significantly higher than the survival rate of location L3.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the season and time of the study which was at the peak of rain and other factors like over dampness of the farm could lead to an increase in bacteria. This could be beneficial to the survival of *Archachatina marginata*. The prevalence and population of the various bacteria groups could be used to assess soil fertility. Kazeev (2006) reported that many fertile soils have high bacteria count. Bacteria infestation could also be detrimental to the survival of snail as a result of bacteria induced diseases. Bacteria diseases caused by *Pseudomonas* spp especially *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* causes intestinal infections in snail. It causes mortality and affects the normal growth and development of snails (Cobbinah, *et al*, 2008). The loss of *Archachatina marginata* due to bacteria infestation will lead to ecosystem disruption.

There was heavy presence of *Pseudomonas* in location L3 which must have resulted in the high mortality recorded. A further study of bacteria species using more modern technology to obtain a detailed view of microbial diversity and using different sampling method is recommended as an extension of the investigation in the future. Since nematodes co-exist in soil with microbes, it is necessary to also carry out a study on the effect of nematodes on Snail Survival.

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